

IMPORTANCE OF SPORT ACTIVITIES IN LEISURE TIME AND SCHOOL SETTINGS AMONG SWISS AND FOREIGN CHILDREN

Results from a cross-sectional study in Central Switzerland

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to observe the importance of sport activities among 5th grade pupils in the canton of Schwyz (located in Central Switzerland) and to identify possible differences between children of various nationalities. The cross-sectional study was carried out in 30 randomly selected classes during the school year 2015/2016. The sample ($n = 468$) consisted of 52.8 % boys and 47.2 % girls, aged 10.8 ± 0.7 years old. Socio-demographic characteristics, interests and participation in sports were established using a standardized questionnaire. The majority of the observed primary school children (85.7%) participate regularly in sports. Approximately 5 hours of sports are practised on average per week; about 18 % are engaged in such activities for more than 7 hours. The percentage of fully sport-abstinent children is around 3.5 %. In accordance with other studies, the influence of immigration backgrounds seems to be mainly moderated by gender. While boys with foreign or Swiss origin are equally enthusiastic about sports, there is clearly a lower level of participation in sports in general and especially in sports clubs among girls who come from an immigrant background. Therefore, they should be considered one of the important target groups for exercise promotion programs.

Key words: Participation and interest in sports, primary school children, nationality, Central Switzerland

Introduction

Despite the variety of today's leisure-time opportunities and increased use of digital media in daily routine, sport and physical activities still play an important role in the leisure-time settings of children and adolescents, and are very popular [3, 7, 10, 14, 18]. Sport in all its various organized and informal forms is a key component of a healthy lifestyle [23] and there is no other age group beside children which is so tightly bound to the sport system [19].

Studies show that socio-demographic characteristics such as gender, age, nationality, social-economic status and parents' sports affinity are major predictors of young people's level of interest and participation in sports [2, 3, 4, 9, 10, 11, 14, 21]. There is consistent evidence which demonstrates that boys and younger children show a higher involvement.

Moreover, children from socially disadvantaged groups with immigrant backgrounds (especially girls), and with parents who have a low sport-affinity, clearly have a lower level of sports participation than children from privileged and sport-active families. Furthermore, sociological sport research regarding the correlation of sport, ethnicity and gender has become more intense in recent years. According to the current level of knowledge, sport and physical activities are also an important aspect of leisure-time among children with immigrant backgrounds, but primarily for boys [1, 4, 12, 14, 15, 16, 22]. While foreign boys show the same level of interest as native youth, girls from an immigrant background are clearly less sport-active and underrepresented in sport clubs as well. Besides gender, sport participation also depends on the country or region of origin [14, 16, 20]. According to reference studies from Germany and

Switzerland [4, 14], most of the girls from South-Eastern and Eastern Europe are considerably less sport-active and tend to be sport-abstinent more frequently. Moreover, some results from our neighbouring states of Germany and Austria indicate that there is also a correlation between immigrant status and motoric capability [8, 24], i. e. children from an immigrant background (especially girls) show poorer performance compared to native children.

So far, there are only a few studies in Switzerland conducted at primary school age, which analyse the importance of sport activities during leisure time and the school setting among Swiss and foreign children. With this background, the following questions will be addressed:

- a) *How important are sport activities during leisure time and school settings for children?*
- b) *Are there differences in sport participation and sport clubs membership between nationality groups and*
- c) *What is the role of gender concerning sport activities?*

Methods

Procedures and participants

This study is based on a cross-sectional survey in primary schools in the canton of Schwyz (Central Switzerland) focusing on the situation of physical education (PE). After the approval of the educational authority, a cluster sample (based on the cantonal school statistics) consisting of 30 classes of 5th graders was randomly selected. Information from the relevant teachers was obtained in cooperation with the local school administration. Participation of pupils was voluntary, but presupposed the written consent of their parents. The study was conducted from September 2015 to June 2016 and followed a standardized procedure. Each class was supervised by our research team. The pupils needed 19 minutes on average to complete the standardized questionnaire. The definitive dataset included 468 children (aged 10.8±0.7 years), representing a participation rate of 95 %.

Measures and analysis

The short questionnaire included several questions about physical education at school

(which are not an objective of this sub-analysis), socio-demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality and the country of origin of foreign children), the sportiness of the children, and the importance of sports in school and leisure time settings. Duration and frequency of children's sport activities were measured with the questions: "Are you a member of a sports club?" (Answer categories: 1 = no, 2 = former member, 3 = yes, in one sports club, 4 = yes, in more than one sports club) and "How often do you practise sports during your free time (outside school)?" (Answer categories: 1 = never, 2 = seldom, 3 = weekly). Children participating in regular weekly activity (category 3) completed this question by specifying their sports involvement (days and hours per week). For detailed analysis, foreign children were classified (following the general categories of the Swiss federal statistical office www.bfs.admin.ch) in four groups of origin:

- a) Western and Northern Europe (i.e. France, Germany, Benelux and Scandinavian countries),
- b) Southern Europe (i.e. Portugal, Spain, Italy),
- c) South-Eastern and Eastern Europe (i.e. Balkan countries, Turkey, Ukraine, Russia) and
- d) outside of Europe (Asia, Africa, America).

Data analysis was performed using SPSS (version 24), Chi-Square Test and non-parametric methods (Mann-Whitney-U and Kruskal-Wallis-Test), which were drawn at significant level of $p < 0.05$.

Results

Participation in sports

The majority of children (85.7 %) do sports weekly; only every seventh adolescent is not active in sport, or is seldom active (table 1a). Approximately 5 hours of sports are practised on average per week; about 18 % are engaged for a longer period of more than 7 hours per week. The percentage of fully sport-abstinent children is around 3.5 %. Boys show a significantly higher sport involvement than girls. While the majority of boys (68.8 %) practise sport activities for 3 or more hours per week, the majority of girls (58.3 %) are active for less than 3 hours per week.

Among nationality groups in general no differences were found, but the differentiated

analysis of children from an immigrant background showed a pronounced gender difference: foreign girls are investing 2.8 hours/week on average for sports, which is only half as much in comparison with foreign boys; furthermore, 31.9 % of foreign girls show clearly low sport participation with none or almost no activity (table 1a). Boys of foreign origin participate on average in 5.8 hours of activity time per week, which is practically the same as for native boys (mean: 5.5 hours); Swiss girls, on the other hand, are more active (mean: 4.1

hours) than foreign girls (mean: 2.8 hours; $p < 0.05$). Moreover, a further breakdown by origin groups shows that girls from Western and Northern Europe are equally sportive as Swiss girls with an average of 4.3 hours/week; boys from Western, Northern, Southern- and South-Eastern Europe are even more active than their Swiss colleagues with an average of 6 hours/week. It is primarily girls from Southern, South-East-/Eastern Europe (mean: 2.6 and 2.2) and from outside of Europe (mean: 1.7 hours), who show below-average sport activity.

Table 1a. Participation in sports (outside school time) of 5th grades (n = 468) in canton Schwyz

variables	participation in sports		amount of sports activity/week				mean±sd
	no/seldom	weekly	> 7 hrs.	> 3-7 hrs.	≤ 3 hrs.	0 hrs.	
all	14.3 %	85.7 %	18.0 %	38.5 %	40.0 %	3.5 %	4.8±3.4
boys	10.5 %	89.5 %	25.5 %	43.3 %	27.3 %	3.9 %	5.6±3.5
girls	18.6 % ^{b*}	81.4 %	8.9 % ^{***}	32.8 %	55.2 %	3.1 %	3.8±2.9 ^{b**}
nationality							
Swiss	12.9 %	87.1 %	19.2 %	37.9 %	40.1 %	2.8 %	4.9±3.3
dual citizens ^a	10.5 %	89.5 %	16.7 %	33.3 %	44.4 %	5.6 %	4.7±4.1
foreigners	20.0 %	80.0 %	13.6 %	42.0 %	38.6 %	5.7 %	4.5±3.4
foreign boys	9.4 %	90.6 %	24.0 %	48.0 %	24.0 %	4.0 %	5.8±3.7
foreign girls	31.9 % ^{b**}	68.1 %	0 % ^{b**}	34.2 %	57.9 %	7.9 %	2.8±2.0 ^{b**}

^a Swiss and other nationalities

^b significant differences between boys and girls: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Table 1b. Participation in sports club in comparison to national findings [14]

	canton Schwyz (11y, n = 468)	Switzerland [14] (10-14y, n = 1525)
sports club membership		
All	73.5 %	62 %
boys	78.9 %	70 %
girls	67.4 ^{b**}	53 %
nationality		
Swiss	76.5 %	66 %
dual citizens ^a	89.5 %	58 %
foreigners	60.0 % ^{c**}	49 %
foreign boys	73.6 %	63 %
foreign girls	44.7 % ^{b**}	37 %

^a Swiss and other nationalities

^b significant differences between boys and girls and ^c within groups: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Sports club membership

Overall, 73.5 % are active in at least one sports club (table 1b). Boys in particular, as well as Swiss and citizens with dual nationality are more frequently engaged in sports clubs than girls or foreign children; whereas both differences evolve from a clearly low quota of foreign girls in sports clubs. Their sports club quota of 44.7 % is significantly different from that of young Swiss girls (72.5 %; $p < .001$). Further differentiation in terms of origin groups shows that the percentage of sports club membership among the girls from South-Eastern, Eastern and outside Europe with 32 % and 29 % is much lower in comparison to the girls from Western and Northern Europe (90 %) or Southern Europe (73 %). There are no statistically relevant differences in sport club

participation among boys based on their region of origin.

The importance of school sports

For 54.1 % of all interviewed children, physical education (PE) is their favourite subject in school (table 2). PE has a significantly higher relevance among boys; however, this gender difference mainly results from the low popularity among foreign girls (36.2 %). Analogous to the preceding analysis of participation in sports, the lowest popularity of PE with 36 % and 29 % appears among girls from South-Eastern and Eastern Europe, and from girls who come from outside Europe. However, school sports in general obtain a gratifyingly high importance independent of gender and nationality (table 2).

Table 2. Importance of physical education (PE) and sports in school

variables	PE as favourite subject		Importance of school sports in general		
	yes	no/others	important ^c	unimportant ^c	mean+sd
all	54.1 %	45.9 %	93.6 %	6.4 %	3.4+0.6
boys	59.1 %	40.9 %	92.2 %	7.8 %	3.4+0.7
girls	48.4 % ^{b*}	51.6 %	95.0 %	5.0 %	3.4+0.6
nationality					
Swiss	55.9 %	44.1 %	94.0 %	6.0 %	3.4+0.6
dual citizens ^a	57.9 %	42.1 %	100 %	0 %	3.7+0.5
foreigners	47.0 %	53.0 %	90.9 %	9.1 %	3.4+0.7
foreign boys	56.6 %	43.4 %	90.4 %	9.6 %	3.3+0.7
foreign girls	36.2 % ^{b*}	63.8 %	91.5	8.5 %	3.4+0.7

^a Swiss and other nationalities

^b significant differences between boys and girls: * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

^c including important/rather important and unimportant/rather unimportant respectively

Discussion

In accordance with other sport studies focused on children and adolescents [7, 14, 19], sport activities in leisure time and school settings are highly important for the majority of the interviewed children (tables 1a/b and 2). 85.7 % do sports weekly (outside of the school), 73.5 % are members of sport clubs and 93.6 % of all the children consider sports at school to be very

important or important. The present membership quota remains stable at a high level since the last cantonal study in 2012 with a comparative value of 70.1 % [13]. Although our cross-sectional data does not allow causal conclusions, it seems that cantonal sport clubs and associations are successful in attracting school children as new members. In addition, sport clubs' quotas among the school children observed in Central Switzerland are higher than

at national level; according to a nationwide study in 2014 [14], the proportion of sports club membership among 10 and 11 years old in Switzerland is between 62 and 65 %.

Boys engage more in sports and show a higher quota of sport club membership than girls. In accordance with other studies [3, 4, 12, 14, 15, 22], our analysis confirms that this presumed gender difference has its roots in the clearly lower sport participation of foreign girls, while boys from an immigrant background are as involved in sport as Swiss boys. Nearly one-third (31.9 %) of the foreign girls never or only seldom practice sports in their leisure time; their activity time and sports club quota of 44.7 % are significantly different from that of Swiss girls (72.5 %; $p < .001$). Further differentiation based on the region of origin shows that in particular, girls from South-Eastern and Eastern Europe and from outside of Europe are less active. Girls from these regions seem to have limited access to organized and informal sports. According to findings from German studies [5, 12], this fact of a lower level of socialization through sport clubs appears especially to be influenced by traditional gender roles and cultural-religious values and norms, which are conveyed in the family as well as by low socio-economic status, low level of education and possible language barriers. The overall high relevance of PE independent of nationality and gender (table 2) shows, on the other hand, that foreign girls are not fully dissociated from organized sports. Therefore, school settings offer a good opportunity (for example through voluntary, extracurricular sport courses or target-group-specific offers) to reach especially foreign girls (and also indirectly their parents) and to motivate them to participate in a higher level of leisure time sport activity. However, to make this implementation successful,

relevant gender- and intercultural competence among PE teachers is crucial [6]. Therefore, approaches to heterogeneity in PE classes should be intensified during vocational training and the education of teachers. In addition, sport federations and clubs should also improve cross-cultural competency of the trainers [5, 12, 18].

This study has some limitations. First, the data were collected with a questionnaire. This subjective assessment of sport engagement can lead to general difficulties for children in terms of their ability to realistically estimate their sports behaviour. Also, the tendency of social desirability cannot be excluded [17]. Secondly, due to the cross-sectional design and to the fact that our survey allows no further statements concerning infrastructural, familial characteristics and circumstances, which can have conducive or obstructive influence on sport participation among children, possible reasons can only be the subject of speculation.

Conclusion

The majority of primary school children in the canton of Schwyz are regularly involved in sports. In accordance with other studies, it appears that girls from immigrant backgrounds are less active and are less seldom inclined to participate in sports clubs. Therefore, they should be considered as one of the important target groups for exercise promotion programs. In addition, our findings clarify the need for differentiated analysis in comparative observation of sports participation among children, both local and from an immigrant background. In order to increase the informative value of this research, qualitative aspects should be analysed, as well as findings in the form of quantitative data as set out in this study.

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